

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP3 – Determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation: generation of quantitative and translatable data

D3.11 EMA Qualification Advice: Making the best use of the new nonclinical and in silico predictive tools generated in this WP3 to inform risk assessment on medication use during lactation

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	11-12-2024	First draft
V2.0	16-12-2024	Final version

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Abstract

This deliverable summarizes the key aspects to consider when utilizing the non-clinical and in silico predictive tools developed in Work Package 3 (WP3) of the IMI ConcePTION project. WP3 focused on establishing a platform to predict drug transfer into human milk and consequent infant exposure, utilizing in vitro, in vivo, and in silico methodologies. The deliverable builds on insights from previous work (summarised in D3.10 and other deliverables), and addresses feedback from the European Medicines Agency (EMA), offering recommendations for integrating these tools into regulatory frameworks and clinical practice. While further refinement and ultimately formal validation of the development tools is required, these methodologies carry the promise to thoroughly address uncertainties regarding maternal medication safety for infants when mothers are breastfeeding. This document aims to guide stakeholders in leveraging the tools for improved medication safety assessments during lactation.

Glossary

CL	Clearance, typically expressed in L/h, representing the capacity of a pharmacokinetic process (e.g. hepatic drug metabolism or secretion to milk)
DID	Daily Infant Dosage, daily drug dose ingested by the infant based on an average milk concentration and the volume of milk consumed on a daily basis
hMEC	Human Mammary Epithelial Cells, used in in vitro assays to study drug transfer in milk
mpMEC	Minipig Mammary Epithelial Cells, used for validating milk drug transfer models
M/P Ratio	Milk-to-Plasma Ratio, indicating the concentration of a drug in milk relative to that in plasma
PBPK Modeling and Simulation	Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic Modeling and Simulation, used to simulate drug kinetics in the body
RID	Relative Infant Dose, a measure of infant drug dose via human milk as a percentage of the body weight-normalized maternal dose
SmPC	Summary of product characteristics, representing drug information used to inform the label of a drug product

2. Introduction

The ConcePTION project, launched in April 2019, is a private-public partnership aimed at generating robust evidence about the safety of medications during pregnancy and lactation. Work Package 3 (WP3) specifically developed a non-clinical testing platform to predict drug transfer into human milk and subsequent infant exposure. The platform combines *in vitro* (e.g., hMEC), *in vivo* (e.g., minipig studies), and *in silico* (PBPK modeling and simulation) approaches to address a significant data gap: fewer than 5% of approved drugs include lactation-related data in their labeling.

The absence of lactation data poses a challenge for breastfeeding mothers and healthcare providers, who must balance therapeutic needs against the potential risks of drug exposure to infants. Ethical concerns limit clinical studies in breastfeeding populations, necessitating alternative methodologies to generate actionable safety data.

This deliverable (D3.11) compiles insights from WP3, building on the outcomes of D3.10 and addressing EMA feedback from briefing book iterations. The document outlines key aspects for optimizing the use of WP3 tools in regulatory and clinical contexts, offering a pathway for future qualification and application of these methodologies.

3. Overview of WP3 Outputs

3.1 In Vitro Tools

WP3 developed and evaluated *in vitro* models using hMECs and mpMECs to predict drug transfer across the blood-milk barrier. These models were successfully used to determine apparent permeability coefficients (P_{app}) across cultured mammary epithelial cells, derived either from Göttingen Minipigs (mpMECs) or from human (hMECs). These *in vitro* models were characterized (e.g. for transporter expression at the mRNA level), and also evaluated for functionality with established probe substrates for transcellular, paracellular and carrier-mediated routes.

The *in vitro* models were also applied to evaluate the transepithelial permeability of 10 model drugs, illustrating at least a 10-fold range in permeability values. Transport polarity turned out to be limited, indicating that actual *in vitro* expression and functionality of these transporters may be low compared to *in vivo* conditions (although most relatively lipophilic drugs are unlikely to show significant transport polarity *in vivo* also).

Future endeavors should investigate the impact of presence of (diluted) milk (pH 7.2) and plasma (pH 7.4) instead of simple incubation buffers when determining the Papp values. In addition, quantitative proteomics applied to both *in vitro* and *in vivo* samples could verify the relevant expression of *in vivo* relevant transport proteins in cultured mpMECs and hMECs.

Finally, plasma and especially milk drug binding studies should be conducted with the same model compounds for instance by equilibrium dialysis as an additional approach to take into account binding and sequestration of medication in human milk.

3.2 In vivo Göttingen Minipig model for drug milk secretion

WP3 successfully established a Minipig lactation model to provide quantitative data on drug transfer and systemic exposure in nursing offspring. At the time of completion of this project, an excellent correlation was demonstrated for 4 model drugs (amoxicillin, metformin, levocetirizine, venlafaxin) between the M/P ratio determined in the Minipig model and the clinically observed M/P ratio in humans. Based on a cassette study conducted for another 4 model drugs: acyclovir (administered as valaciclovir), atenolol, levetiracetam and escitalopram, *in vivo* data for a total of 8 compounds will be available to further determine the predictive performance of this *in vitro* model. Importantly, also the systemic exposure of these model compounds in piglets will be documented.

The robustness of this *in vivo* model was confirmed with amoxicillin in a follow-up GLP *in vivo* lactation study including 6 animals, and data were consistent with data obtained in 3 animals as part of the original pilot study.

Of note, the maternal plasma and milk data were also used to develop a population pharmacokinetic (popPK) model for amoxicillin in lactating minipigs. Following compound-specific modifications, the same structural model can be applied to data obtained with other compounds.

The rich *in vivo* data sets obtained in this *in vivo* part of the project will be instrumental also for verifying *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation algorithms, especially since the same compounds were also tested in mpMECs and hMECs (see 3.1).

3.3 PBPK modelling and simulation for drug milk secretion during lactation

A lactation-specific PBPK framework was developed to predict drug kinetics in lactating mothers and breastfed infants. The model integrates data on compound (drug) physicochemical properties, in vitro ADME properties, study design and underlying physiology and allows for:

- 1) **Simulation of human milk concentration-time profiles:** such profiles are then used to generate model-based M/P ratios. For at least 80% of the evaluated model drugs, compound-specific lactation PBPK models were consistent with clinically observed M/P ratios.
- 2) **Estimation of relative infant dose (RID) and daily infant dose (DID):** as the AUC in milk or the AUC in plasma along with the M/P ratio allows to calculate an average concentration of drug in human milk, multiplying this average milk concentration with the daily milk volume ingested by the infant allows to calculate the DID and subsequently, the RID.
- 3) **Exploration of population variability:** PBPK models allow to simulate concentration time profiles taking into account population variability in anatomical (e.g. body size), physiological (e.g. cardiac output) and ADME protein expression (e.g. transporters) parameters. Further characterization of lactating populations will be needed to achieve predictive models in terms of population variability.

Importantly, several implementations of structural PBPK models were tested in the context of this project. This included either using a permeability- versus a perfusion-limited model, as well as the use of bidirectional clearance (CL) values across the blood milk barrier obtained via different approaches. The CL values were estimated either: (i) with a Quantitative Structure Property Relationship algorithm based on physicochemical compound properties as developed by Koshimichi et al. or by Atkinson and Begg, or (ii) by multiplying in vitro determined Papp values (see 3.1) with the in vivo blood/milk barrier surface area. Of note, accurate determination (or estimation) of this surface area (including its interindividual variability) should be subject of future research.

4. Key aspects to be considered for implementing these models

4.1 Regulatory alignment

The EMA QA advice experts emphasized the need for concrete examples to demonstrate the translational value of the models developed in WP3. Generating additional data, that is for additional model compounds, in these model systems will be instrumental.

A further recommendation included aligning the non-clinical platform-based predictions with existing SmPC guidance and integrating outputs with toxicological data to inform risk assessments.

Moreover, the development of infant PBPK models to predict exposure of breastfed infants to maternal medication should be pursued.

4.2 Addressing Challenges

Future endeavours should address continuous evaluation of model performance, especially to reach a stage where the present compound-specific lactation PBPK models can lay the foundation for a robust lactation PBPK framework. Such a framework would support reliable bottom-up (or middle-out) prediction of drug milk exposure of new chemical entities for which no or very limited clinical milk data are available. Development of such a lactation framework will be instrumental for regulatory acceptance.

Depending on the model or combination of models used (e.g., in vitro, in vivo, PBPK), the prediction uncertainty should be further assessed. As IMI Conception's goal was to reduce uncertainty on medication safety during lactation (and pregnancy), this represents a key point of attention.

As also recommended by the EMA expert panel, the context of use of the developed non-clinical platform should be defined. This implies for instance whether the existing models can be applied to small molecules versus other therapeutic modalities (e.g. biologicals have not been tested as part of this project). Considering small molecules, the in vitro models presently do not seem to be qualified for transporter-mediated processes of milk distribution, making this an interesting future endeavour. The context of use-aspect has yet another dimension in that these models developed here can be applied in different stages of the drug life cycle. As an example, early during drug development, the in vitro hMEC-based model may be applied, while the in vivo Göttingen Minipig model can be used for confirmation of the M/P ratio at the later drug development stage. PBPK modelling and simulation can support PK predictions, including for maternal drugs during lactation, throughout the drug life cycle and the PBPK-based predictive performance will gradually improve as development is progressing. Finally, the selection of specific model systems should also depend on the impact the resulting information, as this will differ for a clinical decision versus drug development decision versus a clinical trial design.

4.3 Practical considerations

Experience from non-clinical and computational model development within WP3 also identified the following practical considerations:

- Standardization of experimental protocols across in vitro and in vivo platforms.
- Use PBPK models to extrapolate findings to broader populations and assess variability
- Develop decision trees to guide the use of tools in regulatory workflows.
- Exploit the availability of rich in vivo lactation data sets in Göttingen Minipigs to build lactation PBPK models in this species and translate lessons learned to the human PBPK models

4.4 Recommendations for stakeholders

Researchers should consider expanding the chemical space of tested compounds to enhance model generalizability. In addition, they should integrate proteomics-based characterization of blood-milk barrier transporters into in vitro models.

Recommendations for **clinicians** include using WP3-generated tools to support evidence-based counseling on medication use during lactation. Furthermore, they should consider leveraging RID and DID predictions to evaluate relative safety of drugs. Importantly, the weight of these predictions should be evaluated considering already available information from other sources.

Regulatory bodies could evaluate and establish qualification procedures for WP3 tools, and encourage the use of non-clinical data in SmPC statements when clinical data are unavailable.

5. Conclusion

The predictive tools developed in WP3 represent a significant advancement in understanding drug transfer into human milk and infant exposure. While further validation is necessary, these methodologies carry the promise to offer a robust framework for improving medication safety assessments during lactation. Continued refinement and application of these tools are essential to address the current data gap and enhance regulatory and clinical decision-making. Meanwhile, it appears recommended to start applying this non-clinical platform for clinical decision making, especially for life-saving medicines where no information at all is currently available regarding associated infant risk during breastfeeding.